

1 I19F, 1 I19T, 2 I19V, 1 V19I



0 2 4 6 8 10 12



1 I19F, 1 I19T, 2 I19V, 1 V19I



- I
- F
- T
- V

- shallow
- intermediate
- deep
- NA

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 I19F, 1 I19T, 2 I19V, 1 V19I



- I
- F
- T
- V

- shallow
- intermediate
- deep
- NA

0 2 4 6 8 10 12